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Observed climate change impacts on plant communities in Mediterranean-type ecosystems: A systematic review

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Abstract

Mediterranean-type ecosystems (MTEs) are projected to be among the most vulnerable terrestrial ecosystems to global climate change. Plant community responses in MTEs to climate change scenarios have been well researched using experimental and modelling approaches, yet observational studies of climate change impacts remain less studied. We present a systematic review of observed climate change impacts on plant communities in the five global MTEs, highlighting the key disturbances and drivers of vegetation change, the most frequently reported biological responses to these disturbances, and the prevailing geographic trends. We found a large geographic bias in the overall number of publications ($N_{\text{pub}} = 128$) with only 9% from the Global South, and that disturbances and responses were unevenly represented across the MTEs. Climatic variation, drought, wildfire, frost, and pathogens and insect infestations were the most commonly reported disturbances, largely studied in relation to vegetation condition and growth. Studies on diversity, phenology and physiology were less common, and absent in some regions. We scored studies using a quantitative index that assessed confidence in their methods and findings, and found high scores for detection of climate change-induced biological responses, but lower for understanding of the relationships between climate change impacts and observed responses. The extent to which reported differences among regions reflect different effects of climate change and ecological responses versus research focus and capacity remain unclear. A collaborative research programme that considers generalities and common resilience mechanisms among MTEs will aid our understanding of climate change-induced disturbances and vegetation responses in these global biodiversity hotspots.

Significance Statement

Mediterranean-type ecosystems (MTEs) are among the most vulnerable terrestrial ecosystems to projected climate change. Here, we review the observed climate change impacts on plant communities in MTEs and compare trends across five disturbance classes and response categories. Publication frequency showed a clear geographical bias, with most publications coming from the Mediterranean Basin. Disturbance classes were not ubiquitous across MTEs, and were largely investigated in relation to vegetation condition and growth. Based on a quantitative index of confidence, studies scored highly for detection of climate change-induced biological responses, but lower for understanding of the relationships between these responses and associated climate change drivers. These results provide an important baseline for collaborative research on climate change impacts on vegetation systems in MTEs.

Main Text

Introduction

Mediterranean-type ecosystems (MTEs) are believed to be among the most vulnerable ecosystems to anthropogenic climate change (1, 2), especially under projected climate change scenarios of increasing aridity and temperatures, and increased frequency of extreme events (2). The five MTEs, namely the California Floristic Province (hereafter 'California'), central Chile (hereafter 'Chile'), south- and southwestern west Australia (hereafter 'SWA'), the Cape Floristic Region of South Africa (hereafter 'CFR'), and the Mediterranean Basin, represent unique biodiversity and endemism hotspots containing the world's richest floras outside of the tropics (3–8). In the most recent IPCC Assessment Report 6 Working Group II chapter on terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems (2), less than 3% of all cited literature was directly related to MTEs and the climate challenges faced by vegetation in these regions. Although MTEs were referenced more than in previous reports, and despite the recent cross-chapter paper dedicated to the Mediterranean Basin (9), there remains a scarcity of research on observed climate change impacts on plant communities across MTEs globally. Given their similar climates, it is expected that MTEs may be vulnerable to similar environmental stressors, some of which may be unique to these ecosystems. They share similar complex environmental dynamics attributable to factors such as fire, post-fire recovery intervals, as well as high sensitivity to rainfall and strong seasonality (6, 10–12). Despite a rich literature comparing the ecology and evolution of the five global MTEs (6, 11, 13–16), intercomparisons of climate change impacts and their underlying mechanisms are scarce. Identifying similarities or differences in the observed climate change impacts and underlying mechanisms across the regions could aid our understanding of thresholds of disturbance and ecosystem resilience in response to a changing climate. This information would help us anticipate change, inform mitigation and adaptation efforts, and guide further monitoring and research.

This study aims to synthesise the current state of knowledge on the observed impacts of climate change-related disturbances on plant communities across MTEs and highlight the similarities (or differences) in biological responses across the regions using a systematic review approach. We do not include studies that present results from climate change projections or experiments only. Further, in order to identify research gaps, patterns of research publication frequency (i.e. how many papers have been published) and comprehensivity (i.e. how many disturbances and/or drivers are examined) are explored. We adopt the IPCC sixth assessment report definition of a driver as 'any natural or human-induced factor that directly or indirectly causes a change in a

system' (17), and define a disturbance as an event that causes damage to the structure, health, or resources of a natural system. We expect that similar climate change impacts, and drivers behind these impacts, have been observed across the different MTEs, because they share similar ecological dynamics (18). Where differences are observed, these are likely due to factors unique to each MTE. We also expect that MTEs with smaller research communities and fewer resources (e.g. limited research funding) are likely to have fewer studies and are likely to be under-reporting the number and range of observed impacts and their drivers (13, 19). Following the PECO framework (i.e. population, exposure, comparator, outcome (20)), the key elements guiding the literature search were as follows: Population of interest – terrestrial plant communities in Mediterranean-type ecosystems; Exposure – observed, measurable climate change-related disturbances; Outcome – measurable biological responses of plant communities/vegetation systems. The comparator element of the PECO framework was not defined for the present study since experimental studies, which typically have clearly defined interventions/exposures and comparators, were excluded, and a comparator could not be defined across all possible exposures for the observational studies of interest.

Results and discussion

Literature summary and trends

Searches across two online databases yielded 4638 records from Web of Science and 3998 records from Scopus combined across two search periods (see Supporting Information and Fig. S1 for more details). After deduplication in R (21) and Rayyan (22), 7127 records remained. After screening all publications during Phase I (titles only), a total of 385 publications underwent Phase II screening (titles and abstracts). An additional 14 publications were included from other sources, including three articles identified opportunistically by the primary author, and 11 MTE-relevant publications gleaned from the literature cited in the two most recent IPCC WGII assessment reports (AR5 and AR6). A total of 170 publications were retrieved for Phase III full-text screening. After screening full-texts, a total of 128 publications remained and were included in the analyses. Of the publications included in the review, the earliest were from 2003 (Fig. S2). Publication records remained lower than 10 per year across all regions. The greatest number of publications per year was achieved in 2019, with a total of 14 publications stemming from all regions except the CFR. The overwhelming majority of publications focused on the Mediterranean Basin (n = 88), followed by California (n = 18), SWA (n = 10), Chile (n = 8) and the CFR (n = 4).

The observed bias in publication numbers towards the northern hemisphere was expected, as California and the Mediterranean Basin have larger research communities and generally better

resources for research (13). The Mediterranean Basin has long been proposed as a model region for studying global change impacts on MTEs in general (23), which in conjunction with its large and relatively well-funded research community has likely contributed to the larger volume of publications. Only 17% (n = 22) of publications included in this review were from the southern hemisphere. Of these, only 12 publications were from countries considered to be from the Global South: Chile and the CFR. This result aligns with previous research indicating that the Global South is notably underrepresented in top journals and among top authors in ecological research (24). Geographic reporting biases are well-documented in conservation science (25–27), which is problematic for establishing representative global conservation targets, especially since this often leads to conservation priorities that are poorly aligned with the global distribution of biodiversity (27). Although there exists a cross-chapter paper on the Mediterranean Region from the IPCC WGII sixth assessment report (9), this only covers countries in the Mediterranean Basin and does not extend to other Mediterranean-type regions. Collaborative research networks and integrative research across MTEs offer potential solutions to overcome these limitations (28) and bolster research efforts in the Global South.

Plant responses to climate change-related disturbances

Disturbances and drivers — Five primary climate change-related disturbances were reported. These were climatic variation, drought, wildfire, frost, and pathogens or insect infestations (Fig. 1). Climatic variation here refers to maintained fluctuations beyond the normal range of the climatic variables for study location, while drought, wildfire, frost and the impact of pathogens are considered stochastic disturbance events. Climatic variation and droughts were the most frequently reported disturbances and were reported in all MTEs (Fig. 1), together contributing 67% in the CFR, 68% in California, 73% in SWA, 97% in the Mediterranean Basin and 100% in Chile. Other disturbances, however, were not ubiquitous across all MTEs. We expected that if there were differences in observed disturbances between regions, this is likely due to factors unique to each region. Wildfire was reported in all regions except Chile (CFR n = 1; SWA n = 1; Mediterranean Basin n = 2; California n = 6), despite the Mediterranean zone of central Chile experiencing frequent wildfires (29, 30). The wildfires in Chile's Valparaíso region in early 2024 highlight the link between climate change and other disturbances, and may appear in the literature more frequently in the coming years (31). The influence of pathogens and/or insect infestations was reported only in the northern hemisphere (Mediterranean Basin n = 1; California n = 2). These reports were specifically on bark beetles in California (32, 33) and on fungi and bark beetles in Spain (34). Recent research suggests that bark beetle outbreaks are intensifying in the northern hemisphere driven by climate change (35, 36). Our searches, however, did not

detect the literature around climate change-related insect outbreaks in the southern hemisphere, such as the native *Eucalyptus* longhorned borer, *Eucalyptus* weevil, and gumleaf skeletoniser in SWA (37–39). Furthermore, SWA was the only region to report frost ($n = 2$) (40, 41), which could indicate a vegetation system that is uniquely sensitive to extreme cold or, alternatively, a lack of targeted research resulting in sparse and/or unpublished data in other MTEs around extreme cold events.

While some disturbances are commonly observed and recorded, biological responses to other disturbances have also been investigated but are not reported here, given our specific exclusion criteria. Examples of excluded publications include non-terrestrial studies on the impact of changing water balance on riparian plant communities (42, 43), simulation and modelling studies of projected changes in population dynamics and species distributions under climate change and/or different climate change scenarios (44–46), and experimental studies on changes in nutritional status of plant communities under warming and drought (47, 48). While we explicitly excluded studies that focused exclusively on anthropogenic drivers of change such as agriculture and land-use changes, these drivers were often reported in tandem with or triggered by other climate change-related drivers due to complex feedbacks in social ecological systems and the challenge of decoupling anthropogenic impacts from natural factors (28).

Biological responses to disturbances — Trends in biological responses to the reported disturbances varied considerably among regions (Fig. 2). Many publications reported observed climate change impacts on vegetation condition and growth. The condition response included factors that might affect the health status of a plant and/or plant community. Vegetation condition was largely reported to decrease (i.e. deteriorate) across all disturbances (Fig. 2). Marginal increases (i.e. improvements) in condition were also reported in California across all reported disturbances except for wildfire, and in the Mediterranean Basin with climatic variation and drought, although these increases were minimal.

Decreasing, increasing and non-linear growth trends across the range of disturbances were reported in California, the CFR, SWA and the Mediterranean Basin, while Chile reported only decreases and non-linear changes (Fig. 2). Increasing growth trends arose from a variety of responses, including increased basal area e.g. (49, 50), higher relative growth rate e.g. (51, 52), and increased stand density e.g. (53, 54), among others. In the CFR, growth trends were reported as increasing and decreasing in almost equal measure in response to climatic variation and wildfire. This result stems from a single study and is the result of the complex population dynamics (mortality and recruitment) of the Clanwilliam cedar (55). The CFR also reported a decrease and non-linear changes in growth in response to drought, stemming from a single study

on three different forest types, of which the drier forest was most negatively affected (56). The decrease in growth under drought suggests that the vegetation systems in the CFR and central Chile are sensitive to this disturbance type. Growth responses in the fynbos vegetation of the CFR are varied and determined by the post-fire regeneration stage (12, 57), with drought experiments showing species-specific growth responses particularly within the Proteaceae (57, 58). Similar post-fire regeneration dynamics under extreme drought conditions have been identified in central Chilean Mediterranean forests, where recovery was significantly compromised once a certain drought severity threshold had been exceeded (59). These trends could be further understood by examining the physiological responses of the vegetation systems in these regions.

Changes in diversity, phenology and physiology have been attributed to regional and global climate changes in other ecosystem types with high to very high confidence in the most recent IPCC WGII assessment reports (2, 60), but not all MTEs reported on these responses (Fig. 2). Non-linear trends in physiology were observed in California, Chile and the Mediterranean Basin. No studies reported on changes in physiology in the CFR or SWA. The Mediterranean Basin reported both increasing and decreasing trends in physiological responses to climatic variation and drought, while California and Chile reported decreases in response to drought. Decreases in physiological responses in Chile resulted from reduced hydraulic diameter and lower potential hydraulic conductivity in trees under extreme drought conditions to enhance hydraulic safety (61). In California, decreased physiological responses resulted from declines in NDVI in shrub communities (62) and increased vapour pressure deficit causing tree death (63).

Diversity trends varied between the MTEs under different disturbance conditions (Fig. 2). Diversity decreased in California under drought and wildfire, while declines along with non-linear changes were reported in the CFR under climatic variation and wildfire. Trends varied in the Mediterranean Basin, where large increases in diversity were observed in response to drought and climatic variation, and smaller increases were observed in response to wildfire. Drought had only a very small negative impact on diversity in the Mediterranean Basin. Increasing trends in diversity under drought conditions in the Mediterranean Basin were attributed to canopy defoliation resulting in proportional increases in understorey growth form richness (e.g. shrubs and herbs) (64), and changes in relative abundances of different oak species as well as conversion from deciduous broadleaf forest to shrubland and other forest types (65). Changes in diversity were not reported for Chile or SWA.

Changes in phenological events (e.g. flowering, fruiting and leaf-out times, pollen counts, etc.) were only reported from the CFR and the Mediterranean Basin (Fig. 2). The CFR reported a decrease (i.e. undesirable shift) in phenology under climatic variation. This was based on a single

study corresponding to an 11.6-day advancement in flowering date in the genus *Pelargonium*, largely accounted for by increased mean annual temperature (66). The Mediterranean Basin reported decreases and non-linear changes in near equal measure, and only small increases under climatic variation and drought. Classifying trends in phenological events along a decreasing-increasing scale was necessary for comparison with the other reported responses, but was challenging since phenology covers a broad array of events that can be interpreted in different ways. For example, intensification of *Quercus* pollen season over time was considered an increasing trend (67), while a decline in polycyclism frequency in *Pinus* was considered a decreasing trend (68), and delays in flowering period up until an average-turn-point year and advancing thereafter was considered a non-linear trend (53). These response trends were not guided by the overall interpretation of the value of the phenological change as these were often in conflict, i.e. an increasing trend may have positive or negative outcomes or consequences for people or biodiversity. In some cases, changes in phenology were considered negative, e.g. increased intensity of the *Quercus* pollen season, correlated with increases in atmospheric carbon dioxide and rising air pollution in cities, contributing to potential exacerbation of allergies and respiratory disease (67). Similarly, advancement of flowering phenology relative to insect pollinator appearance implies negative outcomes for pollination rates (69). No studies viewed changes in phenology as positive, however, most did not assign positive or negative values to the observed changes.

MTEs support diverse vegetation types and plant growth forms, often with high degrees of endemism (70), but these were not equally studied across the MTEs, with a bias towards perennial, woody vegetation (Table S5). Studies from the Mediterranean Basin reported mostly on trees, less so on shrubs, and rarely on other growth forms. A total of 16 shrubs and 36 trees were studied at the species level. Studies from California reported mostly on trees (n = 12) and shrubs (n = 7). Chaparral and coastal sage scrub were the most commonly studied shrub vegetation types. Many trees were studied at species level, commonly within the genera *Pinus*, *Quercus*, *Calocedrus* and *Abies*. Studies from SWA reported only on trees, with nine out of 10 papers based in the Northern Jarrah Forest. Most SWA research at the species level was on *Eucalyptus marginata* and *Corymbia calophylla*, but also *E. wandoo*, *E. patens*, *Allocasuarina fraseriana* and *Banksia grandis*. Studies from central Chile reported on shrubs, graminoids, forbs and trees. Three out of eight papers focused on the genus *Nothofagus*, including *N. macrocarpa*, *N. glauca* and *N. obliqua*. *Kageneckia angustifolia* was the only other tree species studied in this region. Studied shrubs include *Berberis montana*, *Escallonia revoluta* and *Proustia cuneifolia*. Studies from the CFR reported on shrubs, graminoids and trees, with three out of four papers from the Fynbos biome and one from Afromontane forest. Of the four papers included, one focused on a

single genus, *Pelargonium*, which comprises different growth forms (e.g. geophytes, herbs, woody evergreens), and one on a single tree species, *Widdringtonia cedarbergensis*.

Small sample sizes and non-reporting of null results make it difficult to discern whether similarities and differences in trends across MTEs are an accurate reflection of their ecology, or whether they are due to the greater number of publications from the northern hemisphere, or general publication and reporting biases. Moreover, sample size decreases even further when investigating these trends at different scales, such as growth form or genus level. Trees were the only growth form studied across all MTEs, yet low numbers of species studied in some regions and differences in the drivers, responses and ecologies of the species still hamper comparison. Hobbs et al. (13) note that comparative studies in MTEs have tended to favour shrub-dominated vegetation, while neglecting grassland, woodland and forest types, all of which commonly occur in MTEs. While this may be true for experimental studies, this review suggests that this trend does not hold for observational studies, which tend to favour forests and tree-dominated vegetation types, and shrublands thereafter. Graminoids, forbs and other non-woody growth forms remain understudied in MTEs likely due to their small size and often non-perennial nature, but are deserving of more attention given their contribution to the overall diversity and endemism in these regions (70).

Confidence assessment and review limitations

Confidence index analysis — To account for risk of bias, we used a modified version of the O'Connor confidence index (hereafter C-index; see Supporting Information and Table S2 for more detail) (71). A wide range of scores were found across the full corpus of literature for the C-index scores (ranging 6 - 20 out of 21) and its four sub-components. The highest possible score for the *prior expectations and alternative causal factors* (SE) sub-component was achieved by 36 publications (28%); for *quality of data to test the expectations* (SD) by eight (6%); for *adequacy of the quantitative or statistical analyses applied* (SQ) by 10 (8%); and for *clarity and completeness in reporting of results* (SR) by 94 (73%) (Fig. 3). Studies from SWA produced scores largely below the overall average, likely due to low data (SD) scores, but they performed well in terms of expectation (SE) scores. Studies from the CFR and Chile, though few, had mostly above average overall scores, with no studies scoring below average in terms of data. Studies from California and the Mediterranean Basin produced scores spanning the full range, including some of the lowest and highest overall scores. O'Connor et al (71) assigned different aspects of the C-index to detection of change versus understanding of how climate affects change (see Table S2). Scores for these aspects varied by region and across biological response categories (Fig. 4). On average, scores were typically higher for detection than understanding. The overall scores show

a common trend of California and the Mediterranean Basin scoring very similarly along both axes, with the CFR being on par along the understanding axis but scoring higher, as does Chile, along the detection axis; SWA achieves the lowest scores along the detection axis, but scores similarly to Chile along the understanding axis. Differences in confidence in reported findings pose challenges for interpretation and cross-regional comparisons of biological responses to disturbances. This underscores the importance of increased collaboration between research communities and regional intercomparisons in MTEs to enhance our understanding and refine methods for detection and inference (72).

Limitations in the search query and included articles may have influenced our review conclusions. We restricted our search to only English-language peer-reviewed publications, which may have exacerbated the geographic bias observed in our dataset, but avoided the difficulties of potential mistranslation and issues around appraisal and reconciliation of grey literature across different geographic regions. Our decision to expressly exclude experimental studies, which form a large part of the climate change impact literature, served to better answer our primary research question around observed climate change impacts (i.e. rather than simulated or modelled impacts). We acknowledge the importance of undertaking experimental research to understand climate change impacts under various projected scenarios for adaptive management and conservation planning. Furthermore, our application of the confidence index assessment (71) was at publication level rather than observation level, with the assumption that the same level of confidence can be applied across all observations in a given study. This was acceptable since we were interested in broad thematic trends rather than individual effect sizes as required when conducting meta-analyses. It is recommended that confidence index assessment also be applied at observation level where possible, which would allow more nuanced interrogation of the reliability of reported climate change-related responses. Additionally, the skew of overall confidence index scores towards detection over understanding of climate change-related impacts suggests that research is more focused on detecting changes rather than understanding their causal factors. The types of ecological research conducted across the MTEs differ substantially, and some studies may not capture the full range of attribution, whether this is intentional or not. While there are multiple studies suggesting frameworks for improving detection and attribution of climate change and confidence in climate change-related responses (71, 72), a greater emphasis on long-term observational research is required, particularly in MTEs where climate change is projected to have a severe and lasting impact.

Conclusions

We report five main climate change-related disturbances across the five global MTEs, with climatic variation and drought being the most commonly and frequently reported. Not all five disturbances were reported uniformly across all MTEs, highlighting that some disturbances are potentially unique to specific regions. Some of this pattern may reflect differences in ecology and vulnerability to climate change impacts, but may in large part also reflect reporting bias. The studied corpus of literature reports on five overarching biological responses – condition, diversity, growth, phenology and physiology – displaying varying trends across regions, suggesting that the vegetation systems across the MTEs respond differently to climate change, despite their similar climates. The studied literature exhibited high confidence index scores for detection of climate change induced biological responses, but lower for understanding of the relationships between climate change impacts (or alternate causal factors) and the observed biological responses. Moreover, the studies included in this review do not investigate the same research questions with the same level of detail, nor at the same spatial or temporal scales across all MTEs, making direct comparisons uninformative. We echo the call for integrative research in MTEs by Arranz et al. (28), who advocate for a collaborative research approach that considers cross-ecosystem generalities and common resilience mechanisms. For example, studies focusing on diversity, phenology, or physiology would improve our understanding of biological responses to climate change. This could facilitate a more holistic understanding of the impacts of climate change-induced disturbances and associated vegetation responses in MTEs over multiple spatial and temporal scales, supporting mitigation and adaptation efforts, and global conservation targets and strategies for these important global biodiversity hotspots.

Methods

Literature search and data formatting

Literature was sourced from two online databases: Web of Science and Scopus. The default collection for each database was searched with no limit on time of publication. The full systematic review protocol was publicly registered with the Open Science Framework (73) prior to screening and data extraction.

Search terms — A broad set of search terms pertaining to Mediterranean-type ecosystems, vegetation or plants, and climate change was searched independently in two online literature databases: Web of Science and Scopus. An iterative process of including, excluding, modifying, and changing the order of search terms resulted in a final Boolean search query as follows: *(mediterranean OR “mediterranean-type” OR “mediterranean climate”) AND (“climate change”*

OR "climatic change" OR "global warming") AND (vegetation OR biome OR ecosystem OR "plant community" OR "winter rainfall" OR "wet winter" OR "dry summer" OR heathland OR fynbos OR "cape flora" OR "cape floristic" OR renosterveld OR "cape lowland" OR chaparral OR "mediterranean shrubland" OR "banksia woodland" OR "oak woodland" OR "coastal scrub" OR matorral OR espinal OR kwongan OR mallee OR karri OR jarrah OR garrigue OR garig OR phrygana OR maquis OR macchia OR tomillar OR batha).

Data export and formatting — All bibliographic data, including keywords and abstract text, were exported from both databases, covering literature up until June 2023 (i.e. round 1). This step was repeated in September 2024 (i.e. round 2), with the search restricted to articles published during the intervening period between June 2023 and September 2024.

All results were filtered to include only peer-reviewed journal articles, data papers or conference proceedings in the English language. While technical reports and grey literature can provide valuable information and data, these were not considered because the quality of these publication types could not be standardised within the scope of this study. Scopus limited the export of data that included full bibliographic information, keywords and abstracts to only 2000 items, so the results were sorted by relevance and only the most relevant 2000 hits were exported for each round of the literature search. As Web of Science did not impose any limitations on data export, all filtered results were exported. Results from both databases were exported in CSV file format.

Data formatting was done in the R statistical environment (21). The two exported datasets were combined and formatted to reflect the same data columns in the same order using the {tidyverse} package (74). A deduplication step was necessary given the expected overlap in content within each database, and also across the two databases. The {revtools} R package (75) was used to deduplicate publications based on titles. The combined deduplicated dataset was then exported for screening purposes.

Further literature was sourced by gleaning cited literature from the two most recent IPCC Working Group II Assessment Reports on impacts, adaptation and vulnerabilities related to climate change: AR5 Working Group II, Chapter 4 (60) and AR6 Working Group II, Chapter 2 (2). A further three publications were identified opportunistically by the author while screening article full-texts (see *Literature screening*). These additional publications were included in the final corpus of literature, and were subject to the same eligibility criteria and screening procedures as the literature sourced from the online literature databases.

Screening and eligibility criteria

Literature screening — The web-based systematic review software, Rayyan (22) was used to facilitate the screening process. Despite completing a deduplication step during data formatting, Rayyan's AI deduplication function was used to provide an additional measure to ensure that no duplicates remained. Both deduplication steps were automated, and all excluded articles were recorded.

A three-phase screening process was followed: screening titles only, screening titles and abstracts, and reviewing full-text articles (Fig. S1). Decisions for all three screening phases were based on the PECO statement and a predetermined set of eligibility criteria (see *Eligibility criteria* and registered review protocol (73)). Any uncertainty in reviewer decisions were discussed among the authors, and final decisions were reached by consensus and expert opinion, based strictly on the predetermined eligibility criteria. Further details about the screening process can be found in the Supporting Information and Fig. S1.

Eligibility criteria — The inclusion of publication types conformed to the procedures on the use of literature in IPCC assessment reports, with priority given to peer-reviewed scientific and technical literature (e.g. data papers) (76, 77). Publications that did not report on the results of data analysis based on observed, empirical ecological data were not considered. Further, publications were not considered if their research questions were not related to observed, measured changes in vegetation (at any level of organisation, e.g. individual species/functional groups, vegetation types, biomes, etc.) as a result of one or more climate change-related disturbances or drivers. Publications that fell within the following categories were specifically excluded: (i) studies that did not relate to the research question and/or PECO statement; (ii) experimental and manipulation studies; (iii) studies that report only simulation, modelling or forecasting of potential climate change scenarios or impacts; (iv) studies that pertained to aquatic (freshwater or marine) or azonal habitats, the latter being communities decoupled from prevailing climate due to special substrate and/or hydrogeological conditions (78); (v) studies that pertained to pastoral/agricultural systems, croplands, plantations or urban environments; (vi) studies that relied solely on remote sensing data without clear links to climate time-series and/or reference to the ecology of the system; (vii) studies that relied largely on paleo-data, or modelled/reconstructed paleo-environments; (viii) studies that reported on physiological changes at individual or species level without reporting or discussing the effects thereof at the community level.

Data extraction and confidence assessment

A data extraction questionnaire was completed for each publication included in the review (Table S1). The questionnaire covered the following broad categories: (i) bibliographic information (four questions), (ii) study design (seven questions), (iii) study system (five questions), and (iv) observations and results (11 questions). This questionnaire served to extract and summarise pertinent data and information from each publication, to be used in the subsequent thematic analysis.

The guidelines described in the confidence index (C-index) framework developed by O'Connor et al. (71) were applied to each included publication. The C-index measures confidence in scientific inferences reported in climate change impact studies, and scores observations along two main axes (i.e. detection of biological change, and understanding of how the biological change relates to climate change) by scoring observations across three sub-components for (i) prior expectations and alternative causal factors (hereafter 'Expectations' or SE), (ii) the quality and/or breadth of available data to test the hypotheses/expectations (hereafter 'Data' or SD), and (iii) the quantitative or statistical analyses applied (hereafter 'Statistics' or SQ). The C-index is applied here as an insightful alternative to the conventional risk of bias assessments found in systematic reviews outside of the environmental sciences, as there was much overlap in the categories of questioning. However, to accommodate several criteria included in critical appraisal tools for environmental evidence (79), the original C-index table (71) has been adapted and applied per publication (rather than per observation) to suit the purposes of this review. Notably, a fourth subscore for 'Reporting' (SR) was added to account for clarity and completeness in reporting of results, along with an additional question each under SD and SQ (Tables S2 and S3, Supporting Dataset S3). C-index scores were grouped by observation and geographic region, and the detection and understanding scores were plotted against each other to visually assess overall confidence in the attribution of the observed responses to climate change.

Data synthesis

Data formatting, analysis and visualisation were conducted in the R statistical environment (21) using the {tidyverse} (74) collection of R packages. A thematic map was generated using shapefiles for 'Mediterranean forests, woodlands, and scrub' ecoregions (80) and the {sf} R package (81). See data deposition information for access to data and code for thematic analysis.

To determine how representative the published data were across the five MTEs, frequency of publications was tallied by geographic region and over time. Then, to assess how MTEs compared in terms of their associated disturbances, the frequency of reports of each climate change-related disturbance was tallied by region. It is worth noting that a single article may report

more than one disturbance. Reported disturbances and drivers were classified into five categories: (i) climatic variation (e.g. increase in maximum daily temperature), (ii) drought, (iii) wildfire, (iv) frost, and (v) pathogen or insect infestation (e.g. beetle infestation, fungal infection). Further, reporting trends were examined across different ecological scales (i.e. growth forms, genera, species), to assess how comprehensively the different vegetation systems are studied within MTEs. Growth form was the broadest unit of comparison between MTEs, given the diversity of ecosystems studied.

To determine how plant communities in MTEs were affected by these disturbances, vegetation responses were categorised according to five biological response categories: (i) condition, which included factors that might affect the health status of a plant and/or plant community, such as assessments of mortality, presence of fungal pathogens or insect infestations, and the presence of invasive alien plants; (ii) diversity, which included responses relating to richness and evenness in a plant community, as well as the presence/absence or migration of species, and their interactions with one another; (iii) growth, including measures of biomass (abundance, cover), morphometrics (size), demographics (density, age), and reproduction; (iv) phenology, which included responses relating to the timing of growth and reproductive events (flowering, shoot burst, fruiting, etc.); and (v) physiology, which captured measures of productivity that were not captured by the 'growth' category, such as nutrient content, chlorophyll concentrations and isotopic fractions (Table S4). Trend directions were assigned as: (i) increasing, (ii) decreasing, (iii) non-linear, (iv) a combination of i-iii, (v) no change, and (vi) not reported. In the case of combined trends, the reported trends were nuanced and did not conform uniformly across two or more studied response variables within the same biological response category. The 'no change' and 'not reported' trend categories were excluded from the thematic analysis. Trends were plotted for each disturbance, grouped by region and biological response category.

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Figures and Tables

Figure 1. Global occurrence of Mediterranean-type ecosystems, showing frequencies of reported disturbances ($N_{\text{obs}} = 154$) and the total number of publications per region included in the review ($N_{\text{pub}} = 128$). The basemap was generated using shapefiles for ‘Mediterranean forests, woodlands, and scrub’ ecoregions (80).

Figure 2. Trends in biological responses of plant communities in MTEs to climate change-related disturbances. Frequencies of decreasing (red), non-linear (yellow), and increasing (green) trends are plotted in stacked bar plots as proportions per disturbance.

Figure 3. Distribution of overall confidence index scores and subscores for expectations, data, statistics and reporting, *sensu* O'Connor et al. (71). A solid black line indicates the mean score and a dashed line indicates the median score across all publications. Axis labels are identical across all plots, but note the difference in axis scales.

Figure 4. Confidence index scores for understanding and detection (mean \pm sd) across all response categories by region. Point size scales proportionately with the number of publications reporting on a particular response. Dashed line indicates the identity line (1:1 slope).